

**IMPACT PERFORMANCE OF POLYMER COMPOSITES: DEFORMATION
PROCESS AND FRACTURE MECHANISMS**

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ABSTRACT

Summarized in this report are the results of our recent efforts in the study of the impact performance of fiber-reinforced polymer composites. Deformation processes and fracture mechanisms of thin-plate composites laminates were examined in relation to material parameters, plate thickness, stacking sequence, and impact loading rate. The deformation process of the fiber/epoxy laminates was found to be closely related to the flexibility of the constituent fibers. In addition, both matrix-fiber interfacial debonding and interlaminar cracking were shown to be effective in dissipating impact energy. Interlaminar hybridization of epoxy laminates with thermoplastic laminates improved the impact toughness of the otherwise brittle epoxy laminates. Due to the poor interlaminar adhesion between PPS and epoxy laminates, post-impact three bending tests show inferior damage tolerance of hybrid-matrix laminates. A simplified theory for impact failure mechanisms of composite laminates is proposed. It provides a mechanistic basis for the development of a practical model for the prediction of impact failure modes. Depending upon the failure mechanisms involved, two different equations were developed for a critical penetration speed of projectile in terms of composite physical constants, laminate geometry, and projectile size. This theory has proved to be useful in the studies on the impact penetration of more brittle composites.

I. INTRODUCTION

The ability to predict material behavior under impact loading is very important in the design and manufacture of ballistic protection products. The penetration resistance of the composites under either low velocity or high velocity projectile impact conditions has been a subject of many research efforts [1-3]. A useful framework for understanding and conceptualizing the deformation process and failure mechanism can be obtained from an instrumented impact testing. The various changes of the failure mechanisms during impact loading are characterized by contours of the times (displacements) to reach the events of material deformation and failure. The progress of the deformation process and the changes of failure mechanisms can be summarized in terms of the numerical values in the load-displacement-energy diagram. Although there has been substantial work aimed at impact dynamics and damage mechanics of the composites [4,5], there is relatively little fundamental study on either the processes by which the composites deform through the laminate or the mechanisms which might control the failure modes in impact testing. The objective of this paper is to investigate the effects of constituent material properties on the mechanisms of crack initiation and propagation. In addition, a simplified theory for the impact fracture process is developed. Based this theory, a dynamic failure criterion is proposed to predict the failure modes of the composites during impact loading.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

Three groups of laminates were fabricated. The first group consists of bare fabric laminas and corresponding single-, two-, and five-layer epoxy laminates. The specimens in the second group are two-layer hybrid-fiber epoxy laminates. In the third group, hybrid-matrix laminates were prepared from epoxy and polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) prepregs. A Dynatup I-730 Instrumented Drop Weight Impact Test System was used to conduct all of the impact tests in the present study. Post-impact three-point bending tests were performed to study the impact damage tolerance of the composite sample. SEM analysis was conducted on a large number of test samples to determine the actual failure mechanisms. The experimental details of the composites systems, laminating procedure, and testing conditions are described elsewhere [2,3].

Two groups of Pe and Gr laminates were tested as a function of the laminate thickness/projectile diameter (T/D) ratio. Both the

laminate thickness and the projectile diameter were varied to give various T/D values. The critical speed of penetration for each sample with a given T/D ratio was then obtained by adjusting the height of the dropping weight. Usually between seven and twenty trials were needed before a critical speed V_c , above which full penetration will occur, could be nailed down. The values of V_c were then plotted against T/D to determine the predominant failure mechanisms in a given group of composite laminates.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Fabric-Layer Lamina Vs. Fiber/Epoxy Laminate

A single-layer fiber/epoxy laminate having an epoxy-free center zone of about 3.8 cm diameter is termed a "fabric-layer" lamina or "zero-layer" laminate. The fabrics tested can be loosely divided into two groups in accordance with the macroscopic impact failure mode. The first group, including polyethylene (Pe), Kevlar-49 (Kv-49), and Kevlar-29 (Kv-29), was characterized by a larger area of fabric deformed to form a dome. The second group consists of polyester (Pet), nylon (Nyl), glass (Gl), and graphite (Gr) fabrics. The impact response of this group was characterized by a clean penetration without any significant extent of plastic deformation.

When impregnated with epoxy resin, the single-layer fabric/epoxy laminates exhibited different failure modes. For Pe laminate, the central loading zone of a lamina was found severely deformed and protruded on the back surface to form a dome. A tremendous amount of impact energy was absorbed even by a single layer of Pe fabric/epoxy laminate. Contrarily, both types of Kevlar fabrics seemed to lose their flexibility, with the deformation zone restricted to a size comparable with the diameter of the projectile.

Although, without epoxy, each of Nyl, Kv-49, and Kv-29 "zero-layer" laminates absorbed slightly higher impact energy than Pet "zero-layer" laminate, only a small debonding area was found on each of Nyl, Kv-49, and Kv-29 single-layer laminates. On the other hand, an additional dagger-shaped whitened pattern beyond the center damage zone was clearly seen in Pet laminate. This matrix-fiber interfacial debonding phenomenon seems to be capable of dispersing a fair amount of impact energy, making Pet laminate performed the second best (next to Pe) upon impact loading.

As the number of layers in a laminate increases, the strength of

each laminate increased slowly. As shown in Figure 1, for the Kv-29, Kv-49, Gr and Nyl fabrics, which experience an initial reduction in single-layer laminate, the values of maximum load pick up very quickly as the number of layers increases. However, even with five layers, the maximum load of Kv-29 laminate is only slightly greater than that of "fabric-layer" lamina, and the maximum load of Kv-49 laminate is still lower than "fabric-layer" lamina. Similar trend is observed in terms of total absorbed energy, E_t , and energy absorbed at maximum load, E_m .

The impact response of a laminate with brittle fiber (e.g. Gr) is characterized by a clear-cut penetration with little interfacial delamination or permanent deflection, and the total absorbed energy is relatively low. If the laminate is flexible but not tough, such as Nyl/epoxy laminate, the impact response exhibits some extent of stress whitening. During the crack propagation, small extent of fiber-matrix debonding and delamination occur. As a result, although the compression modulus is lower than that of the graphite composite, Nylon/epoxy composites absorb more total energy due to the higher strain-to-failure.

The Pe/epoxy laminates, being flexible and tough, shows a high degree of fiber elongation and the indentation rim is extended to form a dome without being fully penetrated. After the initial indentation, the laminate responds quickly in flexure and, combining with high ductility and strength, experienced a high degree of plastic deformation. Therefore, Pe/epoxy laminate has a high total impact energy.

Figure 2 shows two types of fiber-matrix interfacial effect on impact performance of a composite laminate. When impregnated with epoxy resin, the maximum load, P_m , and thus the total energy absorbed, E_t , of Nyl, Gr, and Kevlar laminates drop significantly, then increase slowly as number of layer increases. On the contrary, P_m and E_t of the Pe, Pet, and Gl laminates increase with the impregnation of epoxy resin.

This result suggests the important role of fiber-matrix interface in the mechanical property of a polymer composite.

B. Impact Performance of Hybrid-Fiber/Epoxy Laminates

By varying the composition and stacking sequence of fiber/epoxy laminae, the impact performance of hybrid-fiber laminates can reveal important information concerning the interlaminar fracture process of a composite laminate under impact loading conditions.

The results reveal that the fracture process starts with a linear elastic deformation followed by three stages of plastic deformation, each stage corresponding to different deformation process and failure mode. Indenting perforation, delamination, and back-surface tension cracking are the three primary failure modes observed in this study. One of these mechanisms causes the first significant break in the impact load-time curve while combinations of these mechanisms are responsible for the wavy portion of the curve. Flexural deformation to form a dome in Pe laminates was found to provide a large energy absorption capability.

C. Impact Performance of Hybrid-Matrix Composites

The feasibility of adding thermoplastic prepreg layers to improve the impact toughness of thermosetting matrix composites was investigated. Impact performance of hybrid-matrix laminates suggests that the brittle behavior of thermoset composites, e.g., epoxy laminates, can be improved by incorporating thermoplastic laminae, e.g., PPS prepregs, into epoxy prepregs. However, the poor bonding between the thermoplastic and thermosetting laminas causes the poor impact damage tolerance of the composites. Visual inspection of the samples after 3-point bending showed large amounts of interply delamination within many different layers of each sample and little fiber rupture across the impact point. As reported previously [3], epoxy bonds to the fibers much better than PPS and exhibits a rather brittle failure mode. Poor bondings between PPS and fibers as well as between different matrix prepregs cause ply delamination across the impact area. The residual thermal stresses caused by the differential thermal contractions between different matrices could also be partially responsible for this extensive delamination phenomenon.

D. Materials Characterization by Instrumented Impact Testing

1. Ductility Index

The basic information obtained from instrumented impact tests are P_m and E_t , which are used to evaluate the impact strength and toughness, respectively. The impact properties of the composite laminates in this paper indicate an important phenomenon concerning the impact toughness of these materials. That is, a higher value of P_m which is dictated by the strain energy density of the constituent fibers leads to a higher E_t . This relationship demonstrates that the impact toughness, represented by E_t , is controlled by the in-plane strength of the laminate.

However, an increase of P_m in load-time curves generally causes an increase in E_m and a decrease in E_p . Therefore, higher impact toughness due to higher P_m results in a lower value of DI (defined as the ratio of E_p to E_m).

On the other hand, a composite with ductile raw materials will have a high strain-to-failure, which often leads to high energy absorbed after maximum load, E_p . Thus, impact toughness can also be improved by an increase in strain-to-failure and leads to a higher value of DI.

An example of the composites which have higher DI as impact toughness increases is the "interleaved" composites [6]. In this case, because the projectile penetration of a composite laminate is a fiber-dominated phenomenon, incorporating interleaf layers into the composite laminate has little effect on the value of P_m . However, because of the addition of interlaminar resin layers, the impact load drops gradually after P_m , thus both strain-to-failure and E_t increase significantly, leading to a higher DI.

2. Effect of Loading Rate

Indentation tests using an Instron universal testing machine were conducted over four decades of crosshead speed. Visual examinations show that the laminates reinforced with Gr, Kv, Pet, and Nyl fibers were perforated. The perforation growth in these laminates was limited to the direct-impact area. On the other hand, Pe composites was bulged out along the rim of annular support to form a dome.

Load-displacement curves at various crosshead speeds showed that, as loading rate decreases, P_m increases while E_p decreases. At a high loading rate, the material failure upon impactor indentation is too fast to allow for a flexural response of the laminate. Therefore, P_m is reached quickly and followed by a relatively long duration of fracture propagation. As the loading rate decreases, the composite laminate responds with a sum of indentation deformation and flexural displacement. Therefore, P_m is higher than that at high loading rate. However, as soon as the maximum load is reached, the laminate fails in a relatively brittle mode and the total energy absorbed is approximately the same as that at high loading rate.

E. Impacted Failure Mechanisms of Composites

1. A Simplified Theory

Consider the laminates for use as stand-alone armor for defeat of fragments. A useful index for ballistic resistance of a target

plate is the critical projectile velocity (V_c). The impact velocity of the drop tower is varied in such a way that a critical velocity (i.e. V_c) can be defined, above which the laminates are to be fully penetrated.

Two principal physical mechanisms were postulated by Bless et al [7] for defeat of glass fiber composites (GRP): (1) shear failure around the periphery of the penetration cavity and (2) compressive flow around the penetrator. If one assumes that the first mechanism is the dominant one, then the force on the projectile can be written as:

$$F = \pi D \chi \sigma_{tr} \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

where πD is the circumference of the penetration cavity, χ is the penetration, and σ_{tr} is the effective transverse or through-the-thickness strength of the target laminate. The energy required to penetrate the target is obtained by integrating Equation (1) from $\chi=0$ to $\chi=T$ (laminate thickness) and this is equal to the critical kinetic energy of the projectile:

$$(1/2) m V_c^2 = (1/2) (g D^3 \rho_p) V_c^2 = (\pi/2) D \sigma_{tr} T^2 = (\pi D \sigma_{tr}) \int_0^T \chi d\chi \quad \text{---- (2)}$$

where g is a shape factor and ρ_p is the density of the projectile. The critical speed is therefore obtained by

$$V_c = (T/D) (\pi \sigma_{tr} / g \rho_p)^{0.5} \quad \text{----- (3)}$$

If, instead, the compressive failure mechanism dictates the impact penetration process, then

$$F = (\pi/4) D^2 \sigma_c \quad \text{----- (4)}$$

$$(1/2) (g D^3 \rho_p) V_c^2 = \int_0^T (\pi/4) D^2 \sigma_c dx = (\pi D^2 / 4) \sigma_c T \quad \text{----- (5)}$$

where σ_c is the effective compressive strength. Manipulations of Equation (5) lead to

$$V_c = (T/D)^{0.5} (\pi \sigma_c / 2 g \rho_p)^{0.5} \quad \text{----- (6)}$$

implying that the critical velocity V_c is proportional to the 0.5 power of T/D .

2. Model Calculations

Equations 3 and 6 suggest that by plotting the experimental data of V_c versus T/D one can determine the controlling failure mechanism from the slope of the curve. Figure 3 is a plot of V_c vs. T/D for Gr/epoxy laminates. The critical penetration speed, V_c , was determined by judiciously adjusting the height of the falling weight. Visual observations and microscopic examination confirmed that the graphite fabric-epoxy laminates failed by the cross-shaped cracking mode.

The V_c and V_c^2 of Pe/epoxy composites are plotted as a function of T/D ratio in Figures 4a and 4b, respectively. Both diagrams do

not show a straight line as predicted by Equation 3 or 6. This suggests that other energy absorbing mode(s) are either unnegligible or actually predominant. Examination of the failed specimens has shown the existence of an additional interfacial debonding zone beyond the center loading area. In addition, a dome exists where material has been severely deformed. These tow mechanisms appear to dominate the impact failure behavior of Pe-epoxy composites. Therefore, neither Equation 3 nor Equation 6 will be applicable to the case of low-velocity projectile impact of Pe-fiber reinforced composites.

F. CONCLUSIONS

1. The test results of "fabric-layer" and "multi-layer" fiber/epoxy laminates demonstrated that fiber-matrix interface plays an important role in the impact performance of polymer composites. Furthermore, the permanent deformation of a composite laminate can be divided into three stages, each corresponding to different deformation process and failure mode. Indenting perforation, delamination, and back-surface tension cracking are the three primary failure modes observed. Flexural deformation to form a dome in a large-diameter fixture also provides a large energy absorption capability.
2. Impact performance of hybrid-matrix laminates suggests that the brittle behavior of thermoset composites, e.g., epoxy laminates, can be improved by incorporating PPS matrix prepregs into epoxy prepregs. However, the poor bonding between the PPS and epoxy laminas causes the poor impact damage tolerance.
3. For the impact tests of this study, the increase in the total energy absorbed, E_t , is mainly accounted for by an increase in the energy dissipated before maximum load, E_m . In other words, higher stiffness (i.e. higher P_m) of the composite, not the higher ductility, increases the toughness of the hybrid composites. Therefore, ductility index, defined as E_p/E_m , decreases with an increase in E_t .
4. As the loading rate increases, the front indentation will dominate the fracture process and the impact response reaches the maximum load before the material deforms to the maximum flexibility. This results in a lower value of maximum load and a relatively high ductility. Polymer fiber epoxy composites show higher effect of loading on impact

performance due to the higher flexibility of the fibers.

- Examination of the failed laminates showed that interfacial debonding, delamination, and high extent of plastic deformation play important roles in impact failure process of composites which consist of the fibers with high material flexibility. Therefore, the two equations used to describe the impact failure mechanisms based on the proposed simplified theory, may be applicable only to the impact behavior at high impact speed or that of composites with a high material rigidity.

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Figure 3. Critical velocity (V_c) vs. ratio of laminate thickness to impactor diameter (T/D) for Gr/epoxy laminates.

Figure 1. Maximum load vs. number of layer for fiber/epoxy laminates.

Figure 2. Load vs. time curves of zero-, single-, and two-layer laminates.

Figure 4. (a) Critical velocity (V_c) and (b) square of V_c vs. ratio of laminate thickness to impactor diameter (T/D) for Pe/epoxy laminates.